

The Leap of Aspirations: A Critical Analysis of the Implication of Relocating the National Capital on the Sustainability of Democracy in Indonesia

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Abstract

This research aims to critically analyze the implications of the preparation, formation, and division of the administration of the National Capital on the sustainability of democracy in Indonesia. The research uses a qualitative approach with a case study method within a critical research framework. Data collection was conducted through a literature study analysis of documents describing the preparation, formation, and administrative division of the National Capital City. The researcher proposes two categories of library sources: primary and secondary sources. Primary library sources refer to official documents such as underlying legislation and official state publications concerning the historical process of establishing and dividing the administration of the National Capital. Secondary library sources refer to mass media news documents regarding the preparation, formation, and division of administration of the National Capital as well as journals and books related to democracy and proceduralism. This research concludes that the preparation, formation, and division of the administration of the National Capital are carried out entirely through the delegation of power from the executive agency. Additionally, the legal product of the preparation, formation, and division of the administration of the National Capital reconstructs procedural democracy in Indonesia. The final implication is that the preparation, formation, and division of the administration of the National Capital do not demonstrate efforts at democratization through legal proceduralism mechanisms. A new deliberation institution is needed that actively represents substantive aspirations that are justified through law so that the check and balance function remains legal through legal proceduralism.

Keywords: Legal Proceduralism, National Capital, Procedural Democracy,

Introduction

The Special Capital Region of Jakarta, as the capital city, is unable to fulfill its optimal role in providing security, protection from natural disasters, and a sustainable, decent living environment for its citizens. This is due to uncontrolled population growth, environmental degradation, a decline in living comfort, and uneven economic growth outside Jakarta and Java Island (Monoarfa 2021: 5). The relocation of the National Capital is deemed necessary. Ultimately, President Joko Widodo (Jokowi) announced the new location of the National Capital in two districts in East Kalimantan, namely Kutai Kartanegara Regency and North Penajam Paser Regency (Detikcom 2022). This discourse is not new, as it has been proposed in several previous administrations. President Soekarno, during the inauguration of Palangka Raya as the capital of Central Kalimantan Province in 1957, proposed the idea of relocating the capital to Palangka Raya to ensure that regions outside Java Island did not feel excluded administratively and economically from Java Island (Riana 2019). During President Soeharto's administration, this discourse was raised again with the selection of the Jonggol area in West Java Province as the location for the new capital (Riana 2019). The idea of relocating the capital was brought up again in October 2010 by President Susilo Bambang Yudhoyono (SBY). SBY offered three options to address the congestion problem in Jakarta. First, to maintain Jakarta as the capital with the condition of a complete overhaul. Second, to retain Jakarta as the symbolic capital but move the center of government to another region.

During Jokowi's administration, the discourse re-emerged at the end of his first term, specifically in 2017. This plan was discussed privately in 2018 and publicly announced for the first time in the president's state speech. In that speech, the plan to relocate the capital was to be realized as a National Strategic Project (PSN) during his second term. The reasons for relocating the capital during Jokowi's administration are actually correlated with previous

government plans. These reasons were outlined in the president's state speech on August 26, 2019, as follows:

Firstly, the burden on Jakarta is currently too heavy as the center of government, business center, financial center, trade center, service center, as well as the largest airport and seaport in Indonesia. Secondly, the burden on Java Island is becoming increasingly heavy with a population already at 150 million or 54 percent of Indonesia's total population, and 58 percent of Indonesia's GDP economy is concentrated on Java Island, which also serves as a source of food security. This burden will become even heavier if the capital city remains on Java Island... The third question is, why is it urgent now? We cannot continue to allow the burden on Jakarta and Java Island to increase in terms of population density, traffic congestion that has already become severe, and air and water pollution that we must address immediately. And this is not the fault of the Jakarta Provincial Government, no, but rather due to the large burden placed on Java Island and Jakarta by Indonesia's economy. The economic disparity between Java and areas outside Java continues to increase, even though regional autonomy has been implemented since 2001. (Humas, 2019).

The selection of the new capital location in East Kalimantan was also explained as follows::

There is a question of why in East Kalimantan? First, minimal disaster risks, including floods, earthquakes, tsunamis, forest fires, volcanic eruptions, and landslides. Second, its strategic location in the middle of Indonesia. Third, it is close to already developed urban areas, namely Balikpapan and Samarinda. Fourth, it has relatively complete infrastructure. Fifth, 180,000 hectares of government-owned land are available (Humas, 2019).

After the speech, the government systematically realized the relocation and development of the National Capital Nusantara (IKN). The first step was to include IKN in the list of National Strategic Projects (PSN) through the Coordinating-Minister for Economic Affairs Regulation No. 21/2022 concerning amendments to the Coordinating-Minister for Economic Affairs Regulation No. 9/2022 regarding changes to the PSN list. By including the construction of IKN in the PSN list, IKN automatically became part of the National Medium-Term Development Plan (RPJMN).

This relocation of IKN was not without controversy. On the social media platform X, various sentiments, both positive and negative, emerged in the form of tweets (Sutoyo and Almaarif 2020). Additionally, a survey conducted in 2019 showed that 45.3% of respondents did not agree with the IKN relocation plan (Median 2019). In that survey, the five most common

reasons for respondents' rejection of the IKN relocation were: (1) solve the economy and unemployment first (15%); (2) state expenditures could increase (14.2%); (3) there are issues in Papua (9.3%); (4) building from scratch would be costly (8.5%); and (5) it's too far away (4.9%) (Median 2019). Another survey conducted by the Urban Development Study of the School of Strategic and Global Studies (SKSG) at the University of Indonesia in 2022 also showed similar responses. The study, which captured the perceptions of business actors regarding the impact of the capital relocation on Jakarta and IKN, found that 73.2% of respondents did not support the IKN relocation, while only 26.8% supported it. Furthermore, 80.4% of respondents disagreed with the IKN construction project being funded by the state budget (APBN) as part of the national economic recovery program, while only 19.6% of respondents agreed (Anggoro 2022). Various criticisms have also emerged in the public sphere on this issue. Rendy A. Diningrat, a researcher from the SMERU Institute, wrote in *The Conversation* that the plan to relocate the capital from Jakarta to outside Java, although it had been planned since President Soekarno's era, was poorly executed due to weak underlying logic. This weakness primarily relates to the goal of equitable development and reducing the burden on Jakarta, as well as the lack of transparency in presenting data and comprehensive analysis regarding the implications of the plan (Diningrat 2019). In 2019, the Institute for Development of Economics and Finance (INDEF) held a public discussion titled "Challenges of Social, Economic, and Governance Issues of the New Capital." Dr. M. Fadhil Hasan, a senior economist at INDEF and a speaker at the discussion, outlined several key points on this issue. Besides the weak purpose of the IKN relocation, the monopoly of the discourse by the central government, which is a significant political decision requiring criticism, input, and consensus from various parties, was also highlighted.

Despite the issues in the discourse on IKN relocation, the central government's decision remained firm, in contrast to public discourse. To provide a legal basis for the IKN relocation

plan, President Joko Widodo sent a presidential letter (surpres) regarding the IKN Bill to the DPR on September 29, 2021. The surpres, along with the draft IKN Bill, was submitted by the Minister of State Secretary Pratikno and the Minister of National Development Planning (PPN) Suharso Monoarfa to the DPR Chairperson Puan Maharani (Farisa 2022). Two months after the surpres was sent, the DPR formed a special committee (Pansus) consisting of 56 members, including 6 leaders from various sectors and commissions (Farisa 2022). On January 3, 2022, five members of the IKN Bill Special Committee conducted a working visit to Kazakhstan as part of a comparative study on the process of relocating the National Capital. On January 17, 2022, the IKN Bill Special Committee held a meeting to discuss the National Capital Bill, which ended on January 18, 2022, in the early hours of the morning. In the meeting, 8 out of 9 political party factions agreed to bring the IKN Bill to a plenary session of the DPR. The IKN Bill was finally officially passed into law as Law No. 3 of 2022 (UU IKN) at the DPR plenary session on January 18, 2022, in the afternoon. The UU IKN that was passed consists of 11 chapters and 44 articles covering all matters related to the relocation of the National Capital and the administration of government in the National Capital. This has triggered various public reactions. Even the legality of this law was tested in the Constitutional Court (MK), where the petitioners argued that the stages were too quick for discussing a bill related to the highly strategic and impactful IKN (MKRI 2022).

Apart from the process of formation, the material aspects of the regulation also did not escape controversy. First, Article 4 paragraph (1) letter b explains that the National Capital is led by the IKN Authority, which is an institution equivalent to a Ministry tasked with administering the government of the National Capital. This Ministry-level institution shows a clear distinction between the IKN power institution and regional autonomy. Second, the appointment of the head of government in the National Capital is made by the president. The IKN Authority, led by the Head of the IKN Authority, is at the level of a minister, appointed, and dismissed by the

president (Article 5 paragraph 4). Third, the general elections (pemilu) held in the IKN only cover National elections. In Article 5 paragraph 3, it is stated:

"Excluded from other regional government units, in the Nusantara Capital City, only national-level elections are held."

This explains that in the IKN area, elections are only conducted to elect the DPR, Regional Representative Council (DPD), and President, indicating partial autonomy. This arrangement differs from the capital being in DKI Jakarta Province, where, according to Article 1 point 3 of Law 29/2007, the DKI Jakarta Provincial Government is the Governor and the provincial apparatus of DKI Jakarta as the implementing elements of the DKI Jakarta Provincial Government. And in Article 1 point 4 of Law 29/2007, it explains that the DKI Jakarta Provincial Regional People's Representative Council (DPRD) is a regional representative body as an element of the provincial government. This partial autonomy also provides a difference in the system of checks and balances as well as supervisory functions in the IKN government. The roles of the President and DPR in overseeing the IKN Authority exclude the role of the DPRD. This type of authority model has drawn public criticism. For instance, Mohammad Novrizal, a Constitutional Law lecturer at the Faculty of Law, University of Indonesia, argued that the absence of the DPRD and the absence of elections for the IKN Authority head is undemocratic (Aditya 2022). To assess how democratic something is, one of the benchmarks used is the existence of legal rules and procedures and the use of a legal framework in the ongoing government (Coston 1998: 491). Therefore, anchored in the paradigm of Procedural Democracy, understood as a mechanism for controlling power through processes (Goodin & Pettit 2019: 147). Yusril Ihza Mahendra, in his journal titled "The Paradox of Democracy in Indonesia in 2014-2019: Procedural and Substantial Analysis" (2021), argues that procedural democracy in Indonesia has actually been achieved, such as open elections and universal public participation. However, how the legitimacy of open elections and universal public participation that occurs actually implies the reproduction of centralistic law. This research seeks to trace

the principles of democracy in legal proceduralism in the preparation, formation, and division of the administration of the National Capital and consider the implications for the sustainability of democracy in Indonesia.

The researcher uses the procedural democracy approach to read the framework of democracy in Indonesia in the context of the preparation, formation, and division of administrative power over the IKN because the legitimacy formed is based on legal legality. Moreover, Article 1, paragraph (3) of the 1945 Constitution states that Indonesia is a rule of law state. The procedural democracy approach has many perspectives, so the researcher needs to select an approach that fits Indonesia's democracy. In the literature exploration conducted, the researcher found that Robert A. Dahl's perspective on procedural democracy can reconstruct the procedural democracy framework in Indonesia. This consideration is based on his concept of polyarchy, which provides a picture of the potential of procedural democracy into forms of state management that could occur in Indonesia. Robert A. Dahl, in an article titled *Procedural Democracy*, explains that democratization in a country starts from associative principles. This associative assumption is described as follows:

"assuming that each of a number of persons has in mind the idea of forming an association for certain purposes or changing an already existing association in order to adapt to conditions as they now understand them. Among other things, the association will have rules or will make decisions about rules that are to be binding on the members. Anyone to whom the rules apply is defined as a member" (Goodin & Pettit, 1997: 147).

The initial assumption, which presupposes a need for association to form binding policies, shows the first principle of procedural logic (A1). This principle suggests that there is a need among members and prospective members to make binding decisions on certain issues, requiring a process that results in binding decisions on those issues. The consequences of the first principle of procedural logic have two aspects. First, at least some of the problems in the members' minds can be satisfactorily addressed if at least some members are influenced to act

or refrain from acting in certain ways. Second, the necessary actions to address these problems can be achieved if there is a procedure by which members, or some of them, can decide on rules, policies, goals, principles, actions, or patterns of behavior that members are obliged to act consistently with. The rules, policies, goals, principles, actions, or patterns of behavior produced are obligations imposed on all members and prospective members, so actions that are considered violations of these rules have binding consequences. The second principle of procedural logic (A2) explains that the process of making binding decisions requires two stages: Setting the Agenda and Deciding the Outcome. Setting the Agenda is the process of selecting issues that form the basis of decision-making. This process includes choosing to refrain from making decisions on the issue, making it a temporary decision. This process also involves political activities such as discussing issues, reaching agreements, and even voting results. Deciding the Outcome is the final decision-making process on whether a decision should be implemented or not. This process also produces binding and legitimate decisions. The third principle of procedural logic (A3) states that binding decisions may only be made by their makers (members). Decision-makers are members qualified to make and participate in binding decisions. It is not possible for binding decisions on members to be produced by an association outside the association that has the issues or subjects experiencing the issues. The fourth principle of procedural logic (A4) asserts that valid equal claims justify equal distribution. This means that every issue raised by a member about a problem must be equally considered by other members. This logic suggests that every member of an association has a responsibility to resolve issues within that association, regardless of which member raises the problem. The fifth principle of procedural logic (A5) states that the claims of a large number of members regarding rules, policies, etc., to be adopted through binding decisions are legitimate. All decisions on policies formed within the association are legal and must be adhered to by the members and subjects of the problem.

With these principles of logic, procedural democracy has several criteria. The first criterion is political equality. All procedures proposed to make binding decisions must be based on equality. In a state context, citizens (Demos) must be able to express opinions and choose equally as individuals. Adherence to policies must also be enforceable on all members who make and are subject to the problems. The second criterion is effective participation. Every member bound in the association should have a sufficient role in decision-making and decision execution. The opportunities provided in the association must consider the most appropriate outcomes. If the quick outcome is achieved by complicating other members' decision-making, it fails to meet the first criterion. The third criterion is Enlightened Understanding. For Dahl, setting the third criterion is an outcome of ensuring the previous two criteria and serves as a strong indicator of how well procedural democracy functions. Political equality among citizens constructively shapes wise behavior patterns. With wise behavior patterns, the guarantee of effective participation in procedural democracy encourages citizens to grow in determining, maintaining, and understanding the needs for public policies appropriate to the problems. The process of Setting the Agenda and Deciding the Outcome is a political space that fosters rationality development, encouraging citizens to be wise. The condition of wise citizens in shaping political equality and effective participation achieves the main goal of democracy, according to Robert A. Dahl, which is democracy as rule by the people. If the third criterion is met, according to Dahl, the association has entered the category of "full procedural democracy with respect to its agenda and in relation to its demos." To ensure the running of the category of procedural democracy "full procedural democracy with respect to its agenda and in relation to its demos," Dahl proposes the fourth criterion: control of the agenda. In Dahl's view, rule by the people ensures and encourages every citizen to act as a watchdog of procedural democracy. Every policy and decision issued by the government is subject to full capacity and power by citizens to reject and support every decision and policy. However, Dahl emphasizes that control

of the agenda is determined by the ability and limitations on citizens' power over decisions and policies correlating with government democratization. Thus, citizens play an active role in delegating power that may potentially be managed non-democratically. The fifth criterion is that every citizen in the association is an adult and not a transient. The fifth criterion is based on a static principle of equality. Dahl believes that for proper inclusiveness to exist, the association must exclude considerations of race, religion, ethnicity, and inter-group relations. However, to ensure that citizenship can be claimed appropriately, Dahl proposes a basic standard for the fifth criterion:

"Equal Consideration for all members: No distribution of socially allocated entities whether actions, forbearances, or objects is acceptable if it violates the principle that the good or interest of each member is entitled to equal consideration" (Dahl 1997: 159).

By emphasizing "equal consideration," Dahl explicitly includes rationality as a reference in determining whether an individual can be considered a member of the government. However, dependence on the standard of rationality creates problems. The fundamental problem is how to determine the correct indicators for rationality standards. Dahl modifies the approaches of Locke and Rousseau, known as Contingent on Competence, in determining the status of citizenship. This modification is known as the Modified Categorical Principle, which states:

"Every adult subject to a government and its laws must be presumed to be qualified as and has an unqualified right to be a member of the demos" (Dahl 1997: 157).

Through a rationalization process that considers inclusivity, Dahl's fifth criterion surpasses previous procedural democracy theorists.

the objective of this research is to demonstrate how the preparation, formation, and division of the administration of the IKN can influence the sustainability of democracy in Indonesia, grounded in legal proceduralism, which can be analyzed from the perspective of Procedural Democracy. this research also aims to provide a critical analysis of the implications of the

preparation, formation, and division of the administration of the IKN on the sustainability of Democracy in Indonesia. The preparation, formation, and division of the administration of the National Capital gradually reconstruct legal proceduralism in Indonesia. In addition, the researcher seeks to deeply analyze the delegation of power and legal mechanisms involved in the preparation, formation, and division of the administration of the IKN.

METHODOLOGY

The research method used in this study refers to qualitative research with a case study model. Qualitative case study research is a research method that examines one or more cases in depth. Case studies are not used to test hypotheses, but hypotheses can be generated from case studies (Mohajan 2018: 11-12). Data collection was conducted through literature studies on documents describing the preparation, formation, and division of the administration of the National Capital. The researcher categorized library sources into two categories: primary and secondary sources. Primary sources refer to official documents such as legislation and official state publications that provide a historical framework for the preparation, formation, and division of the administration of the National Capital. Secondary sources refer to mass media news documents regarding the preparation, formation, and division of the administration of IKN, journals, and books related to democracy and proceduralism. The data obtained were used as the basis for analysis and interpretation to understand the case study.

The analytical and interpretative approach proposed by the researcher to understand the case study is critical research. Critical research is an in-depth understanding and examination of problematic situations or phenomena using critical social theories to achieve desired social change. There are four categories that underlie the analysis of critical research: (1) critical understanding and in-depth examination, (2) critical explanation and comparative generalization, (3) open discourse and redefinition or transformative action, and (4) reflective-dialectical argumentation (Cecez- Kecmanovic 2010: 447-448). The analysis results can be in

the form of an understanding of the impact of the preparation, formation, and division of the administration of the National Capital on the sustainability of democracy, a critical interpretation of the impact of the preparation, formation, and division of the administration of the National Capital on the sustainability of democracy, and a discussion on the sustainability of democracy.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

This study produced the following research findings. First, the process of preparing, forming, and dividing the administration of IKN was entirely organized by executive power. In the framework of Robert A. Dahl's procedural democracy, the decision-making process for the capital relocation plan was conducted within a partial association that made binding decisions. In the context of state administration, this partial association is referred to as the executive institution. Based on the historical framework of the capital relocation, the president systematically pushed the discourse and realization of the National Capital's relocation. This means that in the framework of the first (A1) and second (A2) stages of procedural democracy, they are entirely located within the executive institution. Symbolically, the preparation for the National Capital's relocation provides legitimacy to the executive institution as the party requiring decisions. The absence of public participation and contestation of ideas in public discourse makes the value of proceduralism function not as an effort of democratization by the people, but rather as a justification for unilateral decisions. Moreover, the DPR (House of Representatives) as a legislative institution was only involved in the stage of formalizing legal legitimacy through the drafting of the National Capital Law (UU Ibu Kota Nusantara). The DPR, as the people's representative institution, did not represent the association's members (in this context, the country) tasked with representing the people's comprehensive aspirations, but rather only represented the existence of the people. In the researcher's analysis, the presence of the DPR is a crucial point in democratization efforts because the involvement of representation

in decision-making strengthens the second (A2) stage of procedural democracy. Although the DPR initiated discussions, these discussions were more advisory and relatively opinion-based. This differs from the concept of setting the agenda because the opinions expressed by experts are the result of the delegation of power from the DPR. This means that political equality in the form of guaranteed opinions as binding decisions is ultimately not achieved. This indicates that the people's representative institution makes the validity of decisions less justified. This, of course, affects the process of democratization. The discussion, which is the essence of setting the agenda, is systemically unjustified and externalized from state affairs. Indeed, the discourse on the National Capital's relocation existed in the public sphere through the president's speech on August 26, 2019, but legal proceduralism as the highest justification was implemented without involving long discourse by the legislative representation. This means that the discourse in the public sphere did not dominate the preparation of the National Capital's relocation plan. Thus, this discourse was not rationalized by the people, either through representation or by the people themselves. Although the formalization of the IKN legitimacy legalized by the DPR represents the fourth (A4) stage of procedural democracy, the DPR still cannot be positioned equally with the executive institution. The DPR could only represent the people's existence, so power could only be delegated through the approval of the executive institution. However, with this hierarchical logic, the people are still required to comply with the formalization of the National Capital's relocation law because the legally formalized decision is a binding decision for every member of the association (A5).

Second, the legal product of the National Capital's relocation reconstructs procedural democracy in Indonesia. The UU IKN passed by the DPR is a legally justified and binding decision. Every article passed by the DPR is a decision that obliges every member (in this context, the people) to comply with the UU IKN. However, the existence of controversial articles mentioned in the introduction defines ambiguous legal proceduralism. The placement

of the Head of the IKN Authority at the ministerial level, as stated in Article 5, paragraph (4), automatically separates the status of regional autonomy. The implication is that control and full responsibility are not based on the people's aspirations but rather on the executive institution's aspirations. This, of course, affects procedural democracy in Indonesia. Through the electoral mechanism, the expression of aspirations is carried out with a procedural perspective. The bottom-up aspiration mechanism is implemented so that decisions formed by the government are absolutely justified by the majority of the people. However, when the Head of the IKN Authority is responsible to the President, the people's aspirations are not directly received by the Head of the IKN Authority, so the people's aspirations have the potential to be mixed with the executive institution's perspective, resulting in a proceduralism that remains top-down. In addition to the perspective of the people's aspirations, the placement of the Head of the IKN Authority at the ministerial level automatically places IKN and its administrative apparatus as exclusive areas and institutions above regional autonomy. This has the potential to create conflicts of decision with the regions. Moreover, the UU IKN, from a hierarchical legal perspective, is above regional regulations (perda).

Third, the preparation, formation, and division of the IKN administration do not show efforts toward democratization through legal proceduralism mechanisms. In Dahl's perspective of procedural democracy, the fifth criterion explicitly provides a clear basis that proceduralism is driven by equality based on equal consideration. The equality of the people and the delegation of power among the people is the main goal of procedural democracy. However, the preparation initiated by the executive institution, the presence of the legislative institution that only gives legal legitimacy through the formalization of IKN, and the Head of the IKN Authority being responsible to the President do not show that power is delegated equally. As a result, the people are unable and do not have the power to control the agenda. The people, as the delegators of power through elections, cannot supervise and select decisions in the

preparation, formation, and division of the IKN administration. This inability is a critical gap because the separation of the people from the government in decision-making has already occurred and is ongoing. The inability of the people to control the agenda, if analyzed in the long term, will weaken effective participation in procedural democracy. This weakness results in the loss of law's function as a control over the association. Law that is not well justified leads to a decrease in the people's willingness to comply with the law. Law ultimately does not function as a decision of the association but becomes a battleground for power and legitimacy among institutions that can justify the law. This impact is a failure in fulfilling democracy's function as an education in wise behavior. A healthy and legitimately justified law by every institution within the association is the most basic source of the formalized state idea. When law does not function properly, the state idea is at risk of being reconstructed. Ultimately, the absence of well-justified and legitimate law further shows political inequality. This inequality affects the overall process of legal procedural democracy. The principle of proceduralism, which should delegate power appropriately, can instead accumulate power to interested parties. The findings of this study also attempt to provide solutions and new alternative considerations in viewing legal proceduralism as a tool to delegate justification and control over institutions with power so that the process of democratization through procedural democracy mechanisms continues.

According to the researcher, the fundamental problem of power inequality in the preparation, formation, and division of the IKN administration is not about specific institutional problems or a procedural democracy system that does not delegate power to every democratic institution as a whole. Rather, it is about how legal proceduralism must continue to be emphasized so that the supremacy of law for every institution can serve as a legitimate source and can delegate power to various institutions. With well-delegated power, the idealization of a democratic state, namely rule by the people, can be achieved. Dahl, in his book *Polyarchy: Participation and*

Opposition, argues that one way to achieve the five criteria of good procedural democracy is to ensure public contestation and public participation in an inclusive government (Dahl 1971:

5). Specifically, Dahl argues:

“I assume further that in order for a government to continue over a period of time to be responsive to the preferences of its citizens, considered as political equals, all full citizens must have unimpaired opportunities:

1. *To formulate their preferences*
2. *To signify their preferences to their fellow citizens and the government by individual and collective action*
3. *To have their preferences weighed equally in the conduct of the government, that is, weighted with no discrimination because of the content or source of the preference.”* (Dahl, 1971: 2)

These three criteria serve as a basic reference that public contestation and public participation must be able to delegate power appropriately to ensure political equality is legally guaranteed. Therefore, in the context of state administration, Dahl proposes several specific guarantees for the establishment of a democratic state. These guarantees are explained in the following table:

Table 1: Requirements in Democratic Institutions

Guarantees for Public Contestation and Public Participation Necessary	Necessary Institutional Guarantees
1. Formulate Preferences	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. freedom to form and join organizations 2. Freedom of expression 3. Right to vote 4. Right of political leaders to compete for support 5. Alternative sources of information
2. Signify Preferences	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Freedom to form and join organizations 2. Freedom of expression 3. Right to vote 4. Eligibility for public office 5. Right of political leaders to compete for support 6. Alternative sources of information 7. Free and fair elections
3. Have preferences weighed equally in conduct of government	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Freedom to form and join organizations 2. Freedom of expression 3. Right to vote 4. Eligibility for public office 5. Right of political leaders to compete for support and contest votes 6. Alternative sources of information 7. Free and fair elections 8. Government policymaking institutions depend on votes and other expressions of preference

Source: Taken from *Polyarchy: Participation and Opposition* (p. 3) by Robert A. Dahl, 1971, Yale University Press

In the table, the procedural democracy requirements are adequately fulfilled. Through elections guaranteed by Law No. 7 of 2017 on General Elections, every citizen has the right to signify preferences by casting their vote for candidates from regional levels like DPD (Regional Representative Council) and DPRD (Regional People's Representative Council) to the national level, such as the president and DPR (House of Representatives). The General Election Law also ensures that public contestation and public participation in choosing candidates are fair and inclusive. However, the formulation of preferences held by the people is not yet perfect. This is because the votes cast do not necessarily represent the substance desired by the people. Elections are only responsible for determining preferences based on vote counts. Although the principle of equality exists by equalizing each individual to have the same vote value, the substance of the voter's preferences is still represented by the candidates during the campaign process. In the framework of procedural democracy, freedom of expression means the ability to formulate preferences guaranteed by binding legal decisions. Ideally, every candidate should be able to make final decisions on policies representing the will of the people. A President, DPR, DPD, MPR, and DPRD officials should be able to formulate policies derived from the accumulation of substantive preferences from their voters. Therefore, Control of the Agenda must be guaranteed by the state in the form of legal procedures. These legal procedures are known as oversight mechanisms. The President is supervised by the DPR under the mandate of Law No. 17 of 2014 on the People's Consultative Assembly (MPR), DPR, DPD, and DPRD (UU MD3), specifically in Article 69 paragraph (1) letter c. Through oversight of the implementation of laws and the state budget (APBN), the performance of the President can be assessed by the DPR, so the legal procedure in controlling the agenda can be achieved. Unlike the President, who can be controlled by an external institution like the DPR, legislative bodies like the DPR can only be overseen by the internal DPR itself, known as the DPR's Honorary Council (MKD), as explained in UU MD3 Article 83 paragraph (1) letter h. Furthermore, the

MKD's function is explained in UU MD3 Article 119 paragraph (2) as an ethics body. Through the mechanism and authority of prevention and supervision (Law No. 2 of 2018 on the Second Amendment to Law No. 17 of 2014 on MPR, DPR, DPD, and DPRD, Article 121A), the DPR internally has the authority to oversee and assess its own performance. This becomes a problem because, under the assumptions of procedural democracy, the DPR has the power to formalize decisions through the legislative process. This means that the control of the agenda conducted by the DPR can only be justified by the DPR itself. The delegation of power at the DPR level is not possible under existing legal procedures. The legal hierarchy produced by the DPR, as well as the DPR's capacity to oversee itself, automatically places the DPR as an institution with a high accumulation of power without external oversight mechanisms.

According to the researcher, the only control space available to the public is through elections. The public's ability to change their legislative representatives is the only control over the agenda. However, this gap cannot address the situation when representative institutions act inconsistently with democratic principles during their term, as reflected when the DPR ratified the procedural decision with an accumulation of unlimitable power, as in the UU IKN. Therefore, the oversight mechanism requires a direct institution with legal guarantees capable of implementing control over the agenda against the DPR and is equal in stature. In addition, this institution must have the duty and authority to oversee the DPR's performance based on substantive assessments of the DPR's legislative products. Although there is a Judicial Review mechanism that can be submitted to the Constitutional Court, as stated in the 1945 Constitution Article 24A paragraph (1) and Law No. 12 of 2011 Article 9, the capacity of the Constitutional Court is not supervision but rather examination. However, if legal proceduralism only refers to Procedural Democracy, the oversight mechanism will be trapped in a Logical Fallacy Ad Infinitum, which is the repeated substance of the oversight mechanism on one institution tasked with overseeing the institution repeatedly. The impact is that the supremacy of law is

increasingly unachievable because the reproduction of law is becoming less valuable. This solution can only be achieved by providing an alternative approach to proceduralism.

The alternative approach to proceduralism refers to the researcher's efforts to fill the gray area in freedom of expression and the inclusivity of opinions that cannot be accumulated in the procedural democracy mechanism, which is only through elections. The accumulation of substantive opinions becomes crucial as the public seeks guarantees that the government acts in accordance with the people's will, which is the essence of power delegation in procedural democracy. Concrete institutions as watchdogs over central legislators, if not balanced by guarantees of public participation and public contestation that are equal, inclusive, and responsive, will only produce inefficient bureaucracy. Therefore, the establishment of procedures must accumulate the abstract forms of public participation, namely discourse. Budi Hardiman, in his book *“Demokrasi Deliberatif: Menimbang ‘Negara Hukum’ dan ‘Ruang Publik’ dalam Teori Diskursus Jurgen Habermas”* argues that a fundamental basis for justifying the existence of a discourse mechanism called Procedural Ratio is necessary.

Hardiman argues:

“What is very important in Procedural Ratio is not the reasonableness of the world order designed by a subject monologically, but the procedure recognized intersubjectively... The mechanism of intersubjective examination and procedures accepted intersubjectively are the formal requirements containing procedural ratio” (Hardiman, 2009: 33).

Through mutual understanding with other subjects, discourse can be rationalized, and validity claims can be validated. Starting from Habermas's view that human actions or social interactions in society are rational (Hardiman 2009: 34), Habermas proposes two categories of discourse: Theoretical Discourse and Practical Discourse. Theoretical Discourse is a communicative space that questions truth claims (*Wahrheitsanspruch*) of theory-empirical statements (Hardiman 2009: 45-46). Practical Discourse is a communicative space that questions the correctness claim (*Richtigkeitsanspruch*) (Hardiman 2009: 46). These two

categories exist as a consequence of communicative actions that emphasize the principles of truth (*Wahr*), correctness (*richtig*), or honesty (*wahrhaftig*) (Hardiman 2009: 37). Furthermore, the consequence of communicative actions in discourse is aimed at consensus. This means that the public can constructively create norms that regulate and evaluate their own behavior. However, practically, formal provisions are needed to emphasize communication procedures. These provisions must be inclusive, egalitarian, and free from domination (Hardiman 2009: 48). This provision differs from the procedural democracy framework proposed by Robert A. Dahl because it starts from different assumptions:

“First, participation in a discourse is only possible if people use the same language and consistently adhere to the logical and semantic rules of that language. Second, equality in obtaining opportunities in discourse can only be realized if every participant intends to reach an impartial consensus and views other participants as autonomous individuals who are sincere, responsible, and equal, not merely as means. Third, there must be generally accepted rules that secure the discourse process from pressure and discrimination” (Hardiman, 2009: 49).

Discourse becomes a communicative arena that supports public participation and has the potential to be a source of substantive legal legitimacy. Through discourse, law acquires a new characteristic beyond being a source of legitimacy based on procedural principles. This principle is that the law is not only a legitimate and binding decision that must be adhered to by all parties but also a result of a communicative process that can be returned to the intersubjective understanding of its targets (Hardiman 2009: 60). Through discourse constructed by the public, the legislative process, which is a practical discussion produced by the public, has legitimacy equal to that of elections at the national level. This is the formal framework of the institution proposed by the researcher. However, this framework is incomplete without an efficient screening mechanism, as it cannot be denied that the accumulation of the entire public's substantive opinions requires substantial political resources. To address this, the researcher proposes a new prerequisite: the formalization of the political public sphere as part of public participation in the democratic process. The political public

sphere refers to the communicative conditions that lead to the growth of practical discourse that is not bound to institutions or organizations (Hardiman 2009: 134-135).

There are two parts to the Political Public Sphere: the "weak public" (*das schwache Publikum*) and the "strong public" (*das starke Publikum*) (Hardiman 2009: 146). The weak public communication structures are informal and tend to be spontaneous. This is because the medium of the weak public consists of various abstract spaces not bound to legal proceduralism. This means that the circulation of organizational opinion supporting public opinion, the right to speak, and demonstrations with discursive processes are the fundamental essence of the democratic process and formalized in legal procedures. Unlike the weak public, the strong public is a political system that accommodates the existence of practical discussions, such as the existence of the executive government, judiciary, and parliament.

In his practical approach, Habermas proposes a model of democracy known as the "dam model" (Hardiman 2009: 148). In this model, the understanding of the state is divided into two: the center and the periphery. The periphery, which is the political public sphere, is generally responsible for discovering, interpreting, and articulating social-political issues as aspirations to the center (Hardiman 2009: 148). The center is the political system consisting of the executive government, judiciary, and parliament, which includes political parties that produce concrete decisions based on the periphery's aspirations (Hardiman 2009: 149). As a result, procedural mechanisms for periphery aspirations are needed. This is where the role of the institution proposed by the researcher comes in. The "deliberative" institution serves as a filter for aspirations from the periphery and the center. This institution actively filters the opinions existing in the public sphere and articulates those opinions through legally binding mandates to the center. The logical implications of the existence of this deliberative institution include: first, substantive opinions that are not accommodated in the procedural democracy mechanism can be captured with the existence of a deliberative institution that functions as a filter for

opinions in the weak public sphere. Second, the existence of a deliberative institution serves as discursive control over the government. The delivery of public sphere opinions solely as a supervisory process of the center's performance, not an attempt to attack central political institutions. The deliberative institution is also not a direct representative institution of the people because its function is to convey public sphere aspirations separated from the relationship with the people themselves. Third, with the presence of a deliberative institution that functions as a messenger and filter of the public sphere, it shows that the delegation of power produced by the center and periphery is not linear. Because the formalization of the public sphere ensures the evaluation of the deliberative institution's performance, the deliberative institution can also be tested against public aspirations by the center. Moreover, the existing practical discourse mechanism provides space for the deliberative institution to correct its internal decisions. This is certainly different from the DPR, which cannot be evaluated based on substantive performance by external parties.

Conclusion

The systematic and legal preparation, formation, and division of the administration of the Nusantara Capital have reconstructed procedural democracy in Indonesia. The president gradually used the power delegated by the people without democratic discussion to begin the preparation, formation, and division of the National Capital's administration. The presence of the DPR as a legislative body representing the entire people did not show its function properly because it could not represent the substantive aspirations of the people regarding the preparation, formation, and division of the National Capital's administration. Instead, the presence of the DPR only served as a representation of the existence of the Indonesian people. Additionally, the legal products resulting from the preparation, formation, and division of the IKN administration have implications for the reconstruction of legal proceduralism in Indonesia. The authority of the Head of the IKN, equivalent to a minister, automatically

separates the status of IKN from regional autonomy. This shows that the relationship between the people and the Head of the IKN Authority is indirect. There is a transfer of control and responsibility from the people's aspirations to the executive institution. The bottom-up aspiration mechanism through elections is hampered because the Head of the IKN Authority is responsible to the President, so the people's aspirations have the potential to be mixed with the executive institution's perspective, resulting in a proceduralism that remains top-down. The systematic and legal preparation, formation, and division of the IKN administration bring about a decline in democracy and the weakening of legal proceduralism as the highest legitimacy foundation. Law that cannot be well justified leads to a decline in public compliance with it. Moreover, the law no longer functions as a result of collective decisions but becomes a tool for power struggles and legitimacy among institutions that can justify the law. The impact is the failure to fulfill the function of democracy as an education in wise behavior. A healthy and legitimately justified law by every institution within society is the foundation of the formalized state idea. However, if the law does not function properly, the state idea can be reconstructed. In the end, the lack of legal legitimacy further shows political inequality that disrupts the overall process of legal democracy. The principle of proceduralism, which should delegate power fairly, can instead accumulate power to interested parties. In addressing this decline, the researcher proposes several systemic solutions. First, the formalization of the public sphere as part of the people's substantive aspirations. Through the formalization of the public sphere, the people's aspirations can be constructed and guaranteed as part of the binding decisions of the state. To ensure the validity of public sphere aspirations, an institution is needed that functions as a filter for public sphere aspirations. This institution actively collects and articulates opinions from the public sphere and forces the center to take action through legal formalization. The implications of the existence of a deliberative institution include its ability to capture opinions that are not accommodated in the procedural democracy mechanism and serve as a control over

the government's performance without attacking central political institutions. Although it does not directly represent the people, the deliberative institution conveys public sphere aspirations separately from the relationship with the people. The delegation of power between the center and the periphery is not linear because the formalization of the public sphere allows for the evaluation of the deliberative institution's performance by the center and the public. The existing practical discourse mechanism allows the deliberative institution to correct its internal decisions.

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